

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 94

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 94

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 94:1 O LORD, God of ^{1a}vengeance, God of ¹vengeance, ^{2b}shine forth! ² "Rise up, O ^bJudge of the earth, Render recompense 'to the proud. ³ How long shall the wicked, O LORD, How long shall the "wicked exult? ⁴ They pour forth <i>words</i>, they "speak arrogantly; All who do wickedness ^bvaunt themselves. ⁵ They "crush Your people, O LORD, And ^bafflict Your heritage. ⁶ They "slay the widow and the ¹stranger And murder the orphans. ⁷ "They have said, "The LORD does not see, Nor does the God of Jacob pay heed."</p>	<p>Psa 94:1 אֵל-נִקְמוֹת יְהוָה אֵל נִקְמוֹת הוֹפִיעַ : ² הַנְּשֵׂא שִׁפְט הָאָרֶץ הַנָּשֵׁב אֶמּוּל עַל-גֹּאֲוִים : ³ עַד-מָתִי רְשָׁעִים אִיהוּהָ עַד-מָתִי רְשָׁעִים יַעֲלֹזוּ : ⁴ יִבְיְעוּ יַדְבְּרוּ עֲתָק וְתֹאמְרוּ כָל-פֶּעַלִי אֲוֶן : ⁵ עֲמֹךְ יְהוָה יִדְכָּאוּ וְנַחֲלֹתֶיךָ יַעֲנֶנּוּ : ⁶ אֲלִמְנָה וְגֵר יִהְרָגוּ וַיְתוּמִים יִרְצָחוּ : ⁷ וַיַּנְּאֲמוּ לֹא יִרְאֶה-יְהוָה וְלֹא-יִבִּין אֱלֹהֵי יַעֲקֹב : ⁸ בֵּינוּ בַּעֲרִים בָּעַם וְכִסִּילִים מָתִי תִשְׁפִּילוּ : ⁹ הַנְּשֵׂעַ אֲוֶן הֲלֹא יִשְׁמַע אִם-יִצְרַח עֵינֵי הֲלֹא יִבִּיט : ¹⁰ הַיִּסְדֹּר גֹּזִים הֲלֹא יוֹכִיחַ הַמַּלְמֵד אָדָם דָּעַת : ¹¹ יְהוָה יִדַּע מַחֲשָׁבוֹת אָדָם כִּי-תִמְנָה הַבֶּל : ¹² אֲשֶׁר־יִתְגַּבֵּר אֲשֶׁר-תִּיַסְרֶנּוּ יְהוָה וּמִתּוֹרַתֶיךָ תִּלְמַדְנֶנּוּ : ¹³ לְהַשְׁקִיט לֹא מִיַּמִּי רָע עַד יִכְרַח לְרָשָׁע שִׁחַת : ¹⁴ כִּי אֵלֹהִים יִשָּׂא יְהוָה עִמּוֹ וְנַחֲלֹתוֹ לֹא יַעֲזֹב : ¹⁵ כִּי-עַד-צָדֵק יִשׁוּב מִשִּׁפְט וְאִתְּרוּ כָל-יִשְׂרָאֵל לֵב : ¹⁶ מִי-יִקְוֶם לִי עִם-מְרַעִים מִי-יִתִּיצֵב לִי עִם- פֶּעַלִי אֲוֶן : ¹⁷ לֹא־יִלְיֵי יְהוָה עֲזָרְתָה לִי כַּמַּעַט אֲשַׁכְּנָה דוּמָה נִפְשִׁי : ¹⁸ אִם-</p>
<p>Psa. 94:8 Pay heed, you "senseless among the people; And when will you understand, "stupid ones? ⁹ He who "planted the ear, ¹does He not hear? He who formed the eye, ¹does He not see? ¹⁰ He who ^{1a}chastens the nations, will He not rebuke, <i>Even</i> He who ^bteaches man knowledge?</p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר-תִּיַסְרֶנּוּ יְהוָה וּמִתּוֹרַתֶיךָ תִּלְמַדְנֶנּוּ : ¹³ לְהַשְׁקִיט לֹא מִיַּמִּי רָע עַד יִכְרַח לְרָשָׁע שִׁחַת : ¹⁴ כִּי אֵלֹהִים יִשָּׂא יְהוָה עִמּוֹ וְנַחֲלֹתוֹ לֹא יַעֲזֹב : ¹⁵ כִּי-עַד-צָדֵק יִשׁוּב מִשִּׁפְט וְאִתְּרוּ כָל-יִשְׂרָאֵל לֵב : ¹⁶ מִי-יִקְוֶם לִי עִם-מְרַעִים מִי-יִתִּיצֵב לִי עִם- פֶּעַלִי אֲוֶן : ¹⁷ לֹא־יִלְיֵי יְהוָה עֲזָרְתָה לִי כַּמַּעַט אֲשַׁכְּנָה דוּמָה נִפְשִׁי : ¹⁸ אִם-</p>

¹¹ The LORD ^aknows the thoughts of man,
¹That they are a *mere* breath.

Psa. 94:12 Blessed is the man whom
^aYou chasten, O ¹LORD,

And ^bwhom You teach out of Your law;

¹³ That You may grant him ^arelief from the ^bdays of adversity,
Until ^ca pit is dug for the wicked.

¹⁴ For ^athe LORD will not abandon His people,
Nor will He ^bforsake His inheritance.

¹⁵ For ^{1a}judgment ²will again be righteous,
And all the upright in heart ³will follow it.

¹⁶ Who will ^astand up for me against evildoers?
Who will take his stand for me ^bagainst those who do wickedness?

Psa. 94:17 If ^athe LORD had not been my help,
My soul would soon have dwelt in *the abode of* silence.

¹⁸ If I should say, “^aMy foot has slipped,”
Your loving-kindness, O LORD, will hold me up.

¹⁹ When my anxious thoughts ¹multiply within me,
Your ^aconsolations delight my soul.

²⁰ Can a ^{1a}throne of destruction be allied with You,
One ^bwhich devises ²mischievousness by decree?

אִמְרָתִי מִטָּה רַגְלִי חֲסִידֶךָ יְהוָה
יִסְעָדֵנִי : ¹⁹ בְּרַב שְׂרָעַפַי בְּקִרְבִי
תִּנְחַמְיָךְ יִשְׁעֵשְׁעוּ נַפְשִׁי : ²⁰
הִתְבַּרְךָ כִּפְסֵא תוֹת יִצָר עָמְל
עַל־יֶחֱק : ²¹ יִגְדוּדוּ עַל־נַפְשׁ צַדִּיק
וְדָם נָקִי יִרְשִׁיעוּ : ²² וַיְהִי יְהוָה לִי
לְמִשְׁגָּב וַיֵּלֶהִי לְצוּר מַחְסִי : ²³
וַיָּשָׁב עֲלֵיהֶם אֶת־אוֹנָם וּבָרַעְתָּם
יִצְמִיתָם יִצְמִיתָם יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ :

²¹ They ^aband themselves together
against the ¹life of the righteous
And ^bcondemn ²the innocent to
death.

²² But the LORD has been my
^astronghold,
And my God the ^brock of my
refuge.

²³ He has ^abrought back their
wickedness upon them
And will ^{1b}destroy them in their
evil;
The LORD our God will ¹destroy
them.

References

Psalm 94:1

¹Or *avenging acts*

²Or *has shone forth*

^aDeut 32:35; Is 35:4; Nah 1:2; Rom 12:19

^bPs 50:2; 80:1

Psalm 94:2

^aPs 7:6

^bGen 18:25

^cPs 31:23

Psalm 94:3

^aJob 20:5

Psalm 94:4

^aPs 31:18; 75:5

^bPs 10:3; 52:1

Psalm 94:5

^aIs 3:15

^bPs 79:1

Psalm 94:6

¹Or *sojourner*

^aIs 10:2

Psalm 94:7

¹Heb *YAH*

^aJob 22:13; Ps 10:11

Psalm 94:8

^aPs 92:6

Psalm 94:9

¹Or *can*

^aEx 4:11; Prov 20:12

Psalm 94:10

¹Or *instructs*

^aPs 44:2

^bJob 35:11; Is 28:26

Psalm 94:11

¹Or *For*

^aJob 11:11; 1 Cor 3:20

Psalm 94:12

¹Heb *YAH*

^aDeut 8:5; Job 5:17; Ps 119:71; Prov 3:11, 12; Heb 12:5, 6

^bPs 119:171

Psalm 94:13

^aJob 34:29; Hab 3:16

^bPs 49:5

^cPs 9:15; 55:23

Psalm 94:14

^a1 Sam 12:22; Lam 3:31; Rom 11:2

^bPs 37:28

Psalm 94:15

¹I.e. administration of justice

²Lit *will return to righteousness*

³Lit *will be after it*

^aPs 97:2; Is 42:3; Mic 7:9

Psalm 94:16

^aNum 10:35; Is 28:21; 33:10

^bPs 17:13; 59:2

Psalm 94:17

^aPs 124:1, 2

Psalm 94:18

^aPs 38:16; 73:2

Psalm 94:19

¹Or *are many*

^aIs 57:18; 66:13

Psalm 94:20

¹Or *tribunal*

²Or *trouble, misfortune*

^aAmos 6:3

^bPs 50:16; 58:2

Psalm 94:21

¹Or *soul*

²Lit *innocent blood*

^aPs 56:6; 59:3

^bEx 23:7; Ps 106:38; Prov 17:15; Matt 27:4

Psalm 94:22

^aPs 9:9; 59:9

^bPs 18:2; 71:7

Targum

Psa. 94:1 The God who takes vengeance is the LORD; the God who takes vengeance has appeared. ² Lift yourself up, O judge of the earth; requite evil to the proud. ³ How long will the wicked, O LORD, how long will the wicked dwell in tranquillity? ⁴ They will gush and speak blasphemy; all the workers of deceit utter disgraceful words. ⁵ They will crush your people, O LORD, and impoverish your inheritance. ⁶ They will kill the widow and proselyte, and they will murder orphans. ⁷ And they said, “Yah will not see, and the God of Jacob will not comprehend it.” ⁸ Consider, you who are fools among the people; and you unwise – when will you gain insight? ⁹ Could it be that the ear was planted, and hears no instruction? Or could it be that he created the eye, and it has not looked at the Torah? ¹⁰ Could it be that he gave the Torah to his people, and when they sin, they are not rebuked? Did not the LORD teach knowledge to the first Adam? ¹¹ The thoughts of the sons of men are known in the presence of the LORD, for they are nothingness. ¹² It is well for the man whom you rebuke, O Yah; and you will instruct him out of your Torah. ¹³ To give him quietness from the days of evil until the pit is created for the wicked. ¹⁴ For the LORD will not abandon his people, nor will he forsake his inheritance. ¹⁵ For justice will return to righteousness, and after it all the upright of heart will be redeemed. ¹⁶ Who will arise for me to do battle with evildoers? Who will stand up for me to dispute with workers of deceit? ¹⁷ If the LORD were not my helper, my soul would almost have dwelt in silence. ¹⁸ If I said, “My foot is slipping,” your goodness, O LORD, will aid me. ¹⁹ In the many thoughts within me, your comforts will delight my soul. ²⁰ Could it be that the throne of deceit will be allied with you? Or could the creature of toil stand against the covenant? ²¹ Evil things will gather against the soul of the righteous man; and they will condemn innocent blood to the judgment of death. ²² But the LORD will be a helper for me; and my God is the strength of my confidence.

²³ And he has turned their lies against them, and he will destroy them in their evil; the LORD our God will destroy them.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is the fifth of eleven Psalms written by Moses. This Psalm was dedicated to the tribe of Gad. Gad was renowned for its military prowess and ability to punish Israel's enemies, especially those that attacked her. The Midrash Shocher Tov Psalm 90 says that the prophet Elijah was from the tribe of Gad. It will be Elijah who brings the advent of the Messianic era. The LORD will appear as the God of vengeance. He will punish the proud and cruel nations (according to the sage Radak). The Talmud (Rosh Hashanah 31a) designates this Psalm as the Song of the Day for the fourth day of the week. This day is when the LORD created the sun and moon. The God of vengeance will punish the idolaters who worshiped these celestial bodies. Moses composed this Psalm as a prayer to bring the day of the Messianic redemption and retribution closer (according to the sage Radak).

Verse one

אֱלֹהֵי-נִקְמָוֹת (el-n'chamot) means "God of vengeance." This name of the LORD also denotes "champion of justice." Israel had a difficult time with the nations that wanted to destroy her. The Jewish people have been in exile and persecution since the Babylonian invasion of Judah. The Holocaust is an example of human cruelty to people devoted to the LORD. In the Messianic era, these nations will be held responsible for what they did and are doing to the Jewish people. The God of vengeance will ensure that they are sent to Sheol and will never be able to hurt Israel again.

LORD, champion of justice, God of vengeance, shine forth.

Verse eighteen

The Psalmist calls out to the Sefirah Chesed for the LORD's loving-kindness.

Whenever I said, "My foot has slipped," You send power from the Sefirah Chesed, O LORD upheld me.

Notes of the Psalm

This Psalm addresses a problem that several other Psalms have addressed and is a question today. Why can evil people thrive in the world? Should not the LORD step in and do something about it? In a materialistic world, people will always rise to a position of power or wealth because they have taken advantage of others. It is evident in American politics. There is also an elite class of people who have obtained their wealth and prestige on the backs of what they call lower-class people. Today the elite are trying to prevent anyone trying to rise from the lower classes from entering the elite. These people loved capitalism and democracy while they built their wealth and power. Today the World Economic council is filled with these people. They do not want new blood in the group because they can show the world the group's true mission. This group is trying to control the world.

The Psalmist asks the LORD why He has not stepped in. The LORD despises people who exploit their brothers and sisters to become powerful and wealthy. To the average person, the LORD appears to remain outside the situation. The answer is that one day the LORD will decide that He has witnessed enough. He hears the cries of the non-elite and will, in His time, send the God of vengeance through the Sefirah Gevurah. That is the beginning of the Messianic era. People holding the world

hostage, the world's elites, will be destroyed and sent to Sheol. The average person will be given a chance to live in a world where everyone can prosper and enjoy.

Moses knew that an elite group would form in the world. Thus, he wrote this Psalm to give hope to the people who are not elite. One day the LORD will correct this situation.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

